

Synthesis, spectroscopic and electrochemical studies of axially ligated aluminium(III) etioporphyrins

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Abstract : Reaction of EtioP with $\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3$ and phenol results in the formation of corresponding axially ligated aluminium etioporphyrins. The products obtained are separated and isolated by chromatographic methods. These axially ligated Al^{III} derivatives are characterized by various spectroscopic techniques.

Incorporation of metal into the porphyrin ring is confirmed by absorption spectroscopy. The axially ligated Al^{III} etioporphyrins are blue shifted as compared to their free base etioporphyrin and have only two visible bands with D_{4h} symmetry. The electrochemical study of EtioP-Al-phenolate reveals the single reversible oxidation and single reversible reduction in CH_2Cl_2 and reaction occurs at $E_{1/2} = +1.375 \text{ V}$ and $E_{1/2} = -1.403 \text{ V}$ as revealed by cyclic voltammogram.

Keywords : Etioporphyrin, aluminium(III), phenol.

Metalloporphyrins have attracted considerable attention because of their interesting biological functions as the active sites of hemoproteins and prosthetic centers where a mechanistic understanding and chemical modeling of their functions have been the central interests. Oxometalloporphyrin species have been implicated as intermediates in the catalytic cycles of peroxidases¹ such as horse radish peroxidase and monooxygenases such as cytochrome P-450². Although simple oxometalloporphyrin complexes of vanadium(IV)³ and molybdenum(V)⁴ are known, these compounds do not undergo the oxygen transfer reactions characteristic of these enzymes. Structural elucidation and an understanding of the global distribution of oxometalloporphyrins would enhance the amount of information obtained from the analysis of oxometalloporphyrins during environmental monitoring⁵.

Aluminium(III) tetraphenylporphyrin possesses a tightly bound axial ligand the nature of which influences the photophysical properties depending upon the spin orbital coupling character of the ligand. The presence of a strongly coordinated axial ligand may cause a few problems, especially if the ligand possesses strong spin orbital coupling properties. Compounds in which axial ligand is derived from phenols can be used to initiate the polymerization of propylene oxide, β -propiolactone and β -butyrolactone giving oligoethers and oligoesters having narrow mol. wt. distribution⁶. Due to the interesting behaviours of aluminium porphyrins, we have aimed at the synthesis, spectroscopic, characterization and

electrochemistry of axially ligated aluminium etioporphyrins in order to understand the steric and electronic effects of the axial ligands on the properties of porphyrins.

Materials and methods :

All reagents used were of A.R. grade and chromatographic separations were carried out with Merck basic alumina. Absorption spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Hitachi U-3400, Lambda 35 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The cyclic voltammograms and differential pulse voltammograms were recorded on a BAS 100-A Electrochemical Analyser. The NaNO_3 , NaNO_2 and KNO_3 used for the preparation of salt bath were procured from Qualigens.

Tris(acetylacetonato)aluminium(III) ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_6\text{Al}$) : Aluminium nitrate (8 g) was dissolved in 50 ml of water and 2.5 ml of acetylacetone was added to it. To the well-stirred solution 2 M aqueous ammonia was added dropwise until the solution was just alkaline. The resultant solution was cooled in ice, filtered by suction and dried in an oven (about 70 °C). The product was taken up in chloroform, filtered and the chloroform was evaporated to obtain tris(acetylacetonato)aluminium(III) [m.p. 192–194 °C (corr.)].

Etioporphinatoaluminium(III)phenoxide : Phenol ($3.086 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol}$), EtioP ($6.602 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol}$; 0.307 g) and $\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3$ ($3.211 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}$; 1.0403 g) were heated in a boiling tube at 240 °C with constant stirring on a salt

bath kept on a magnetic stirrer for two hours. Boiling tube was covered with funnel to avoid evaporation of phenol. The reaction mixture was cooled and dissolved in minimum quantity of chloroform. The resultant solution was extracted using 2 N boiling NaOH solution. This procedure was repeated till the NaOH layer became colourless. Finally washed with water and filtered to remove Na₂SO₄ water from the reaction mixture. The solvent was distilled off at reduced pressure without heating and the absorption spectrum checked. The compound was then passed through chromatographic column of basic alumina and CHCl₃ was used as an eluent. The pure compound was collected and the solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure without heating, dried and finally the compound was recrystallised by dissolving it in CHCl₃ and petroleum ether and dried. The compound was characterized by UV-Vis spectroscopy.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra : The four banded spectrum collapses to a two banded spectrum with *D*_{4h} symmetry in metallated etioporphyrins. In the present study, we have prepared the compounds of Al^{III} etioporphyrins with various phenols. The compounds were degrading fast and the only compound obtained in high purity is EtioP-Al-phenolate. The effect of various organic solvents on the UV-Vis spectra of EtioP-Al-phenolate was studied and the results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Solvent effects on the optical absorption spectra or EtioP-Al-phenolate

Solvents	B-bands	Q-bands
	[λ _{max} (log ε)] nm	[λ _{max} (log ε)] nm
1. <i>n</i> -Hexane	396(5.05)	530(4.32), 572(4.35)
2. Cyclohexane	396(4.90)	532(4.15), 572(4.19)
3. Pet. ether	396(5.05)	530(4.11), 572(4.16)
4. CCl ₄	400(5.41)	532(4.47), 572(4.55)
5. CH ₂ Cl ₂	396(5.37)	530(4.45), 570(4.49)
6. Dichloroethane	404(5.42)	536(4.35), 574(4.34)
7. CHCl ₃	398(5.46)	532(4.37), 572(4.47)
8. Toluene	398(5.43)	530(4.42), 572(4.50)
9. DMF	404(5.35)	536(4.41), 576(4.38)
10. THF	386(5.25), 404(5.25)	536(4.31), 574(4.29)
11. DMSO	390(5.08), 406(5.08)	536(4.41), 576(4.39)
12. Et ₂ O	394(5.01), 406(5.01)	536(4.36), 576(4.36)
13. MeCN	394(5.16), 404(5.16)	536(4.49), 574(4.46)
14. EtOH	390(5.11), 402(5.11)	536(4.32), 574(4.32)
15. Pyridine	394(5.11), 410(5.11)	540(4.32), 578(4.29)

It is clear from Table 1 that axially ligated Al^{III} etioporphyrins are blue shifted as compared to their free base etioporphyrin and have only two visible bands with *D*_{4h} symmetry. This blue shift is due to the various phenolic ligands axially attached to Al^{III}.

It is interesting to note from Table 1, that in polar solvents (1-9), the spectra of EtioP-Al-phenolate shows a single soret band as expected but in the non polar solvents (10-15), the soret band is split, which might be due to some sort of interaction.

Electrochemistry : The electrochemical redox processes of the porphyrins and their metallated derivatives arise primarily from the π-electron system of the macrocycle. The porphyrins generally undergo two successive one electron reversible reduction and oxidation reactions leading to the formation of π-anion and cation radicals respectively. The reversible ring redox reactions can be represented as follows :

The redox potential of the porphyrins depend on a number of factors such as electronegativity and oxidation of the central metal atom, nature of the axial ligand and the basicity of the porphyrin *etc.*^{7a,8}. In addition, substituents on the meso and on β-pyrrole position of the porphyrins have been found to strongly influence the magnitude of redox potentials. Substituent(s) at the phenyl ring(s) of meso-tetraphenylporphyrin is shown to have a minimal influence on the redox reactivity than the substituent at the β-pyrrole carbon atom^{9,10}. In general, the presence of an electron-donating substituent leads to an ease in ring oxidation and makes the ring reduction difficult. On the other hand, the presence of an electron-withdrawing group diminishes the electron density in the porphyrin ring thereby making the ring reduction easier and renders the ring oxidation more difficult.

In case of etioporphyrins where the substitution is at β-pyrrole position, the electrochemical redox studies are quite different. The electrochemical studies on octaethylporphyrin-Al-OH carried out by Kadish *et al.*¹¹ show two reversible oxidation peaks at *E*_{1/2} = +1.28 V and +0.95 V and one reversible reduction peak at -1.31 V. The electrochemical study of EtioP-Al-Phenolate reveals the single reversible oxidation and single reversible reduction in CH₂Cl₂ as in Fig. 1. TBAP (scan rate = 200 mV/s). Thus reaction occurs at *E*_{1/2} = +1.375 V and *E*_{1/2} = -1.403 V as revealed by cyclic voltammogram.

²⁷Al NMR spectroscopy : It has been known that the signals of ²⁷Al NMR are observed in different regions of

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of EtioP-Al-phenolate in CH_2Cl_2 solution containing 0.1 M TBAPF₆ at 300 K (scan rate 200 mV/s).

chemical shifts depending on the coordination number of the aluminium atom¹². Chemical shifts in ²⁷Al NMR do not always correspond to the coordination number of the aluminium atom, but aluminium complexes having similar structures show their signals in a similar region. (TPP)AlOMe has been reported to show its signal at δ 20 ppm in CDCl_3 ¹⁴, in the present synthesized compounds. ²⁷Al NMR spectra were also recorded and exhibit a sharp peak at δ 20 ppm as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. ²⁷Al NMR spectra of synthesized axially ligated porphyrins.

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